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Led by CETEC with 15 partners from 7 countries, this 4-year (€7.4M) Horizon Europe project (2024–2028) strengthens food security and sustainable EU agriculture.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

$P \cdot H \cdot A$ Antastic

Bioactive Polymers
for Healthier Soil

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based and biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams.

EXPECTED IMPACTS

- Reduction of CO₂ emissions from agriculture
- Reduction of plastic pollution
- Better use of bio-fertilizers and bio-pesticides / Increase efficiency of active bio-products
- Increase in biodiversity
- Increase savings of farmers

Each system is enriched with bio-based active ingredients (including amino acids, hydrolysed proteins, microelements, natural elicitors, and beneficial microbes) to promote plant health and soil fertility.

These solutions will be co-designed and tested with end users in both Northern and Southern Europe, reaching demonstration-level readiness (TRL6), following the principles of Safe and Sustainable by Design.